

D7.2 Blockchain-based decentralised P2P framework – Month 18

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The Blockchain-based decentralised P2P framework extends the basic dataspace framework with added access control and contract enforcement mechanisms while adding a clear interface in which to negotiate access to tools and data.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

DSO	Distribution System Operator
PDH	Personalized Data Hub
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
TLS	Transport Layer Security
IDS	International Data Space
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
RAM	Reference Architecture Model

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable introduces the design and an early alpha implementation of the WILSON decentralised peer-to-peer (P2P) framework for data and service interexchange. Most of the deliverable focuses on the planned development and architectural decisions, discussing the implications of integrating this framework into the dataspace developed with eclipse dataspace components, the usage of blockchain and the requirements from stakeholders.

In that regard, the new version of the IDS Reference Architecture Model (RAM) introduces a much more streamlined dataspace with less components which also means that the P2P framework will directly communicate with the EDC connector instead of being realised as components of the dataspace. While the EDC offers a clear approach to dataspace participation with minimal changes to existing infrastructure it also introduces limitations in the granularity of the access control.

A layered approach is proposed that decouples the development of the different components of the P2P framework. The goal is to separate the concerns over the integration between the different components so that changes in one place do not overly affect the overall service and to decouple technical concerns from the user interactions.

Alpha implementation was also discussed, which is focused on highlighting the expected workflows. The goal is to validate the planned implementation with the stakeholders prior to the actual integration with the dataspace and the wider project which will be done in task 8.2.

The conclusions highlight the role of the alpha version in allowing early validation of the intended workflows ensuring a better fit between the proposed solution and pilot needs. It also discusses key limitations in the dataspace architecture and the need for as much endpoint granularity as possible.

2. INTRODUCTION

The WILSON project aims to create a federated digital ecosystem that enables stakeholders in the building and energy sectors to share and consume data and services in a secure and efficient way. Task 7.2 builds on the Personalized Data Hubs (developed in Task 7.1) to design a decentralized framework that connects these hubs into a common dataspace, supporting interoperability, controlled data access, and trusted service exchange.

The motivation for this work lies in the growing demand for interoperable platforms that can bridge diverse systems and organizations. Service providers and building owners often depend on siloed or vendor-specific solutions, which limit flexibility and slow the adoption of new digital services. The framework described here enables participants to interact within a unified dataspace, while ensuring that data sovereignty, trust, and compliance needs are respected.

This deliverable introduces a high level overview of the planned platform while discussing the advantages and disadvantages of this setup. Technically, the solution will be realized through a layered architecture with backend and frontend components. The backend uses a microservice-based design with Spring Boot and PostgreSQL supported by Eclipse Dataspace Connector integration for interoperability with IDSA standards. Its main functions include:

- **Authentication and Identity Management:** supporting Eclipse Dataspace ID, OAuth2/OIDC, and role-based access control.
- **Service Catalog:** where providers can publish and manage services, including metadata and endpoints.
- **Subscription Management:** covering contract negotiation, approval workflows, and lifecycle control of service access.
- **Access Policy Management:** enabling rules for service access, usage conditions, and audit logging.
- **Analytics and Monitoring:** providing insights into usage, compliance, and system performance.

On the user side, a React-based Single Page Application (SPA) serves as the interaction layer. The frontend delivers tailored user journeys for providers and consumers, including service publication, discovery, subscription, and policy management. The design follows WILSON brand guidelines, focuses on accessibility and responsiveness, and integrates seamlessly with backend APIs.

Together, these components form a P2P environment where multiple actors can exchange data and services under clearly defined conditions. Rather than relying on central authorities, trust is supported through federated identity, dataspace standards, and contract-based access. The prototype validates the feasibility of this approach and provides a solid basis for pilot integration and future refinements.

In summary, deliverable 7.2 documents both the conceptual framework and alpha implementation of a decentralized data and service exchange environment. It highlights

how backend microservices, dataspace connectors, and a user-focused frontend can be combined to realize secure and practical access control in real use cases.

2.1. Structure of the Deliverable

The *Deliverable* is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** EXECUTIVE SUMMARY provides the executive summary.
- **Section 2** INTRODUCTION introduces the objectives and context of the P2P framework within the WILSON framework.
- **Section 3** ACCESS CONTROL REQUIREMENTS AND EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE describes the context from the point of view of the pilots and the tool providers.
- **Section 4** ANALYSIS OF DATASPACE ARCHITECTURE analyses the architecture and functionality of the dataspace and how that affects the p2p framework.
- **Section 5** BLOCKCHAIN AND SMART CONTRACT INTEGRATION presents how blockchain will be used in the context of the project.
- **Section 6** DECENTRALIZED DATA AND SERVICES INTEREXCHANGE FRAMEWORK DESIGN explains the proposed high-level architecture and user workflows within the platform
- **Section 7** PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION PLAN outlines the implementation plan and how the P2P framework integrates with the WILSON dataspace, as well as the status of the alpha version.
- **Section 8** CONCLUSIONS provides conclusions and the future work plan.
- **Section 9** REFERENCES lists references that are used in this Deliverable.
- **The annex** ANNEX 1. ALPHA VERSION USER MANUAL contains a manual of the alpha version of the P2P framework.

2.2. Relation with Other Tasks and Deliverables

This deliverable relates to other WPs as follows:

- **WP5–6:** The P2P framework builds upon the dataspace architecture created by T5.1 expanding the user experience and adding blockchain driven smart contracts to the base contract mechanism of the EDC.
- **WP7–8:** The T7.3 and T7.4 collect data and manage the data plane of the pilots by interfacing with the existing systems.
- **WP9–10 & WP11–12:** The P2P framework regulates the access to the tools and services created on this WPs.

3. ACCESS CONTROL REQUIREMENTS AND EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE

The ability to govern who can access which data and services, under what conditions, is central to the success of the WILSON dataspace framework. Access control not only protects sensitive information but also enables trusted business interactions between participants. This requires a balance between data sovereignty, ensuring providers maintain control over their assets and usability, where consumers can discover and subscribe to services without friction. The following subsections analyse the access control needs emerging from the project pilots and the capabilities already available in the tools developed within the WILSON platform.

3.1. Access Control requirements from the Pilots

The WILSON pilots involve a diverse group of actors, including building owners, facility managers, service providers, and external entities such as DSOs and regulators. Each of these stakeholders requires different levels of access. For example, facility managers may need detailed operational data, regulators may only need aggregated reports, and service providers may request specific building datasets under commercial agreements

From these scenarios, several requirements emerge:

- **Data sovereignty** – Providers must retain full control over what data is shared, at which level of detail, and under what conditions.
- **Role-based access** – Consumers, providers, and administrators require differentiated permissions tailored to their role in the ecosystem.
- **Contractual enforcement** – Subscriptions and usage must be tied to explicit conditions such as validity period, usage frequency, or regulatory compliance.
- **Auditability** – All transactions must be logged transparently to support compliance verification and fair remuneration.

These requirements highlight the need for a flexible but enforceable access control system that can adapt to diverse roles and regulatory contexts.

3.2. Access Control requirements from the Tools

The WILSON dataspace embeds several access control capabilities that can be leveraged by the framework. Taking this approach ensures minimizing compatibility issues.

On the backend, authentication is going to be handled via OAuth2/OIDC and Eclipse Dataspace ID, combined with role-based access control (RBAC) to distinguish service providers, consumers, and administrators. The backend will also manage access requests, subscriptions, and policies through dedicated APIs.

On the frontend, these mechanisms are going to be integrated into the user workflows. Service providers can define access rules when publishing services, and consumers are required to accept conditions when subscribing. Pilot owners can also obtain an overview of how their data is used and validate access to their data.

Taken together, the existing infrastructure already supports a complete access workflow: identity verification → policy definition → contract negotiation → runtime enforcement. However, its effectiveness depends on how granularly services and datasets are exposed, reflecting a broader limitation of IDS-based dataspace, including the WILSON dataspace where enforcement is bound to the granularity of data plane endpoints.

What remains challenging is aligning these mechanisms with the inherent characteristics of IDS-based dataspace, where enforcement is ultimately tied to the granularity of exposed data plane endpoints. To address this, it is essential to analyse how the WILSON framework integrates with the broader dataspace architecture, ensuring that policy negotiation, trust management, and contractual enforcement are consistently applied.

4. ANALYSIS OF DATASPACE ARCHITECTURE

The WILSON framework builds on the IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM), where identity, trust, and policy enforcement are handled by dedicated components such as the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC). This section analyses how access control will be integrated into the dataspace architecture, how identity and trust are managed across participants, and how contracts are defined and enforced in practice.

4.1. Integration Points with Access Control

Within the WILSON dataspace, the EDC acts as the bridge between participants, ensuring that service agreements negotiated in the control plane are enforced during data transfer in the data plane. The P2P framework backend will complement this by managing identities, subscriptions, and policies, while the frontend provides the user-facing tools for defining and accepting conditions.

The main integration points are:

- **Identity and Trust** – Federation through Eclipse Dataspace ID and PKI certificates ensures that only verified participants can join.
- **Contract Negotiation** – Subscription requests initiated on the frontend are formalized into machine-readable contracts exchanged via the EDC.
- **Policy Enforcement** – Policies defined in the backend (e.g., frequency, scope, usage rights) are handed to the EDC's policy engine for runtime enforcement.
- **Audit and Compliance** – Logs from both the backend and the EDC provide traceability, enabling reporting and dispute resolution.

This layered approach ensures that contractual conditions are applied consistently across governance (control plane) and runtime execution (data plane).

4.2. Access contracts

Contracts are the mechanism by which participants agree on how data or services can be used. In WILSON, contracts are closely tied to the subscription workflow:

1. **Subscription initiation** – A consumer selects a service in the catalog and submits a subscription request.
2. **Contract negotiation** – The backend communicates with the EDC to establish contract terms, embedding access policies and obligations.
3. **Approval and activation** – The provider validates the request, and once approved, the contract becomes active and governs data access.
4. **Runtime enforcement** – The EDC enforces the agreed policies during data transfer at the level of the exposed data plane endpoints.

A critical limitation here is that the granularity of control is bounded by the granularity of the data plane endpoints. If a provider exposes only a single, coarse-grained API or dataset, then access control can only be applied at that level. To enable finer control, providers must design modular endpoints (e.g., per dataset, semantic category, or resource). This means

that you can integrate into the dataspace without changes to the prior infrastructure, but it also means that you are bound to the granularity of the endpoints.

Despite this limitation, WILSON's integration of backend policy management, dataspace contracts, and user-facing negotiation tools provides a practical and enforceable framework for trusted service exchange.

5. BLOCKCHAIN AND SMART CONTRACT INTEGRATION

Blockchain driven smart contracts provide the logic for automating agreements between participants in the WILSON dataspace. While the Eclipse Dataspace Connector enables policy negotiation and contract definition at the control plane, these contracts require a trustworthy execution environment for enforcement. To this end, WILSON will leverage Hyperledger Fabric as a distributed ledger platform to implement and execute access contracts.

Fabric offers a permissioned, consortium-based approach, well suited for the project's federated environment where all actors (service providers, consumers, administrators) are known and authenticated. By embedding smart contracts into Fabric's, the system ensures that subscription conditions and usage policies are transparently enforced, logged, and auditable across all stakeholders. The following sections describe a high-level overview of smart contract design for the P2P framework.

5.1. Design of Smart Access Contracts

The smart access contracts represent machine-readable agreements covering the conditions of service use. Their design in Hyperledger Fabric aligns with the requirements identified in Section 3:

- **Identity binding** – Each contract is linked to participant identities issued through Eclipse Dataspace ID and authenticated in the backend. Hyperledger Fabric integrates these IDs into its PKI-based membership service, ensuring trust across systems.
- **Service binding** – Contracts are associated with specific service endpoints exposed via the dataspace. This enables providers to define which datasets or APIs are governed by the contract.
- **Conditions of access** – Parameters such as validity period, frequency limits, data scope, and compliance requirements are codified as part of the contract chaincode.
- **Lifecycle events** – Subscription activation, renewal, suspension, or cancellation are tracked as state changes in the ledger, ensuring a shared and immutable history.
- **Audit trail** – Every transaction related to a contract (e.g., policy update, access request, revocation) is stored on the ledger, enabling transparent dispute resolution.

The design philosophy is modular: new business conditions can be added to the chaincode as additional functions without disrupting existing contracts. This extensibility allows the framework to evolve alongside pilot needs.

5.2. Policy Expression and Enforcement via Smart Contracts

In WILSON, policy rules will be expressed in two complementary layers:

1. **Backend and EDC policies** – Defined in the WILSON backend (e.g., JSON-based policy rules) and negotiated through the Eclipse Dataspace Connector. These govern high-level aspects such as who can access which service under what conditions.

2. **Smart contract enforcement** – Encoded in Fabric chaincode, which enforces the runtime behavior of subscriptions by validating access requests against contract parameters.

For example:

- A consumer attempting to call a service endpoint must present a valid contract ID and digital signature.
- The smart contract checks the request against conditions such as expiry date, access frequency, or scope of permitted data.
- If conditions are met, the request proceeds to the EDC data plane endpoint; otherwise, it is rejected and logged.

This dual-layer approach ensures that negotiated policies (control plane) and runtime enforcement (data plane) are consistent and auditable. Importantly, the use of Hyperledger Fabric adds resilience and transparency: no single participant can alter the execution history, and all stakeholders can verify compliance with agreed terms.

5.3. PKI and Identity Management in Hyperledger Fabric

Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) is a framework of cryptographic technologies, policies, and roles that issues, manages, and validates digital certificates and key pairs. It enables entities to authenticate each other, establish encrypted channels, and sign data with non-repudiation using trusted Certificate Authorities (CAs), registration processes, and revocation mechanisms.

Hyperledger Fabric uses a PKI-backed Membership Service Provider (MSP) to authenticate and authorize every participant—organizations, peers, orderers, and client applications—via X.509 certificates. For WILSON, this PKI anchors runtime enforcement to the same identities used at the dataspace control plane:

- **Identity binding:** Eclipse Dataspace (OIDC/OAuth2) identities are mapped to Fabric client certificates either through a lightweight registry (EDC ID ↔ cert fingerprint) or by embedding selected claims as cert attributes for ABAC in chaincode.
- **Certificate lifecycle:** Participants follow standard CA workflows—registration, enrollment, periodic re-enrollment/rotation, and revocation (CRLs/MSP updates). Short-lived client certs are preferred.
- **Transport security:** All channels use mutual TLS. Enrollment (signing) certificates are kept distinct from TLS certificates to simplify rotation and incident response.
- **Key protection:** Private keys for nodes and privileged clients should be hardware-backed (HSM) or, at minimum, encrypted at rest with strict access controls; root CAs remain offline.
- **On-chain checks and audit:** Chaincode verifies MSP ID and attributes on each invocation, and records cert hashes/serials in events, creating a tamper-evident trail that aligns EDC negotiations with ledger-enforced access decisions.

6. DECENTRALIZED DATA AND SERVICES INTEREXCHANGE FRAMEWORK DESIGN

The WILSON P2P framework is designed to provide a secure and extensible environment for the exchange of data and services between multiple stakeholders. It connects Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs), backend microservices, and a user-facing frontend within a federated dataspace, ensuring interoperability and access control across organisations. This section describes the overall architecture, the mechanisms for subscription and data access, and the user interface concept, complemented with diagrams that illustrate the interactions between system components.

6.1. Architecture Overview

The framework extends the IDS-based PDHs into a federated dataspace where stakeholders can publish, discover, and consume services with controlled access. This architecture has four main layers:

- **Data Layer (PDHs):** Each participant maintains a PDH, storing structured data with semantic annotations. PDHs connect to the dataspace via Eclipse Dataspace Connectors, ensuring interoperability and compliance with IDSA standards.
- **Service Layer (Backend):** Implemented in Spring Boot with PostgreSQL, this layer manages service publication, subscription lifecycles, access policies, and analytics. It integrates with the Connector for contract negotiation, data transfer, and policy enforcement as well as financial data management.
- **Interaction Layer (Frontend):** A React SPA that provides tailored interfaces for providers (service publication, client oversight) and consumers (service discovery, subscription, policy compliance).
- **Proxy layer:** A proxy-pass service which adds a TLS envelope to both the interaction layer and service layer as well as to other services which do not natively include TLS.

The architecture is modular: new connectors, policy engines, or analytics modules can be integrated without disrupting the overall system

6.2. Subscription and Data Access Mechanism

The framework uses a subscription model to manage access to services:

1. **Discovery:** Consumers browse the catalog exposed by the backend, populated with services published by providers.
2. **Subscription Request:** Consumers initiate a subscription, submitting required metadata (intended use, duration, etc.).
3. **Negotiation and Contracting:** The backend interacts with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector to formalize an agreement. Policies and conditions are captured in a contract document.
4. **Approval and Activation:** Providers approve requests; the subscription is activated, and access credentials are granted.
5. **Policy Enforcement:** Every request to a service endpoint is checked against defined access policies (frequency, scope, role-based restrictions). Violations trigger denial or logging.

- Lifecycle Management:** Subscriptions can be renewed, suspended, or cancelled, with billing or reporting handled automatically.

This workflow ensures clear responsibilities: consumers request access, providers retain control, and the dataspace enforces fairness and compliance. Figure 3 depicts this workflow. For now, the remuneration of services is only shown in the interface

6.3. Expected user workflows of the platform

We expect the framework platform to be the main interaction point in order to engage services. The three most important flows, for WILSON stakeholders, are service providers managing services, pilot site owners engaging services and pilot site owners managing their data. This will be validated in task 8,2 using the alpha version as a basis.

6.3.1. Managing services

Service providers should be allowed to review all their services and subscriptions and to onboard new services. The framework should check whenever possible if any modifications to the service offering would contradict already existing contracts.

Figure 1 Manage services

6.3.2. Managing pilot data

Pilot site owners should be allowed to review all their service subscriptions and how pilot site data is being used. The framework should check whenever possible if any modifications to the pilot site configuration and exposed endpoints would contradict already existing contracts.

Figure 2 Manage pilot

6.3.3. Subscribe to services

Pilot site owners should be able to subscribe to services from the P2P framework. The frontend will offer a comprehensive description of the service and its data usage as well as other important information such as service cost. The platform should interact with the dataspace to abstract connector management from pilot site owners.

Figure 3 Subscribing to service

7. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION PLAN

This section details the prototype implementation of the decentralised peer-to-peer framework. The solution has been developed with a layered technology stack combining backend microservices, frontend user interfaces, dataspace connectors, and distributed ledger components. Together, these ensure interoperability with IDSA standards, support access policy enforcement, and provide user-friendly interaction with the marketplace of services.

7.1. Technology Stack and Dependencies

The prototype is built on a modular stack that balances scalability, interoperability, and compliance with dataspace standards. Its architecture comprises three principal layers: backend services, a single-page frontend application, and integrations with dataspace and blockchain components. The decoupling between layers is intended to simplify integration with other tools by separating logical concerns.

7.1.1. Backend layer

The backend is implemented with Spring Boot 3 on Java 17, providing the core service logic. It manages user authentication, the service catalog, subscription lifecycles, and access policy enforcement. Persistence is ensured by a PostgreSQL relational database, which supports the schema for users, organizations, services, subscriptions, and access contracts. To handle asynchronous workflows, such as subscription approvals or policy updates, the backend integrates RabbitMQ as a message broker. All services are containerized using Docker, ensuring reproducibility and simplifying deployment in both development and pilot environments.

7.1.2. Frontend layer

On the user-facing side, the prototype includes a React Single Page Application (SPA). This frontend provides role-specific dashboards for service providers, consumers, and administrators. Providers can publish and manage services, consumers can browse the catalog and subscribe, while administrators oversee compliance and approvals. The interface adheres to WILSON's branding and accessibility guidelines, with responsive layouts.

7.1.3. Blockchain and Smart Contracts

For contractual enforcement and auditability, the plan is to leverage Hyperledger Fabric as a permissioned distributed ledger. Service subscriptions and access policies negotiated in the dataspace are to be codified into Fabric chaincode, which guarantees transparency, immutability, and a shared execution history across stakeholders. This layer adds resilience and trust to the enforcement of access conditions.

7.1.4. IDS Connectors and Interoperability

The plan is to align the architecture with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC), which acts as the gateway for cross-organizational interoperability. Connectors negotiate contracts, enforce policies at runtime, and advertise services through the IDS Metadata Broker. The idea is that the decentralized P2P framework will work as an improved access control system on top of the EDC infrastructure.

7.2. Backend Architecture and Implementation

The backend of the framework provides the service logic that underpins user management, service publication, and subscription workflows. At this stage, it is delivered as an alpha version, with only the essential components implemented to allow workflow simulation and feedback collection from pilot site owners. Most of the advanced integrations with dataspace components and blockchain contracts are still planned rather than realised, and the present setup should be understood as a functional prototype rather than a production-ready system.

7.2.1. Current Alpha Implementation

The backend is implemented as a monolithic Spring Boot application running on Java 17. To simplify development and early-stage testing, the system currently uses an H2 in-memory database instead of PostgreSQL. This lightweight setup allows rapid prototyping of entities such as users, organisations, services, and subscriptions without requiring full database infrastructure. Authentication is provided through a basic JWT-based mechanism, and REST APIs expose functionality for service publication, browsing, and subscription requests.

7.2.2. Planned Data Persistence and Schema

While the H2 database is sufficient for demonstration, the long-term plan is to migrate to PostgreSQL for persistence and scalability. The target schema has already been defined and includes support for users, organisations, services, subscriptions, access requests, and policy definitions. This schema will provide the necessary foundation for integration with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector and Hyperledger Fabric, ensuring that backend operations are consistent with dataspace governance and distributed ledger auditability.

7.2.3. API Layer and Future Extensions

The prototype currently supports a limited number of REST endpoints, covering registration, login, basic service publication, and subscription requests. More advanced endpoints for access policy management, contract negotiation, and audit reporting are specified in the design documents but remain unimplemented at this stage. Future iterations will extend the API surface to include integration with the Contract Negotiation API of the EDC, as well as endpoints for interacting with chaincode deployed on Hyperledger Fabric.

7.3. Frontend Architecture and Implementation

The frontend serves as the main point of interaction for participants in the decentralized P2P framework. It has been designed as a React Single Page Application (SPA), providing an

accessible and responsive user interface that adheres to WILSON’s branding and design guidelines. The application ensures that service providers, consumers, and administrators each have tailored interfaces suited to their roles, while maintaining a consistent user experience across devices.

7.3.1. Frontend Core Architecture

The frontend is implemented with React 18, using React Router DOM for navigation and a component-based architecture that promotes modularity and reuse. Styling follows WILSON’s visual identity, with a palette centered on deep blue, yellow, and white, ensuring a professional appearance consistent across the platform. The application is responsive by design, adapting layouts for desktop and mobile displays while maintaining WCAG 2.1 AA accessibility compliance.

7.3.2. Role-Specific Interfaces

The alpha version focuses on the experience of the service consumer as the less technical actor. However, the interface will be organized into workflows that match the different user roles in the ecosystem.

- **Service providers** will be able to register and manage services, monitor client subscriptions, and define access policies. Their dashboard includes components for service creation, editing, and compliance monitoring.
- **Service consumers** will be presented with a searchable catalog of services. They can browse detailed descriptions, request subscriptions, and monitor the status of their active contracts.
- **Administrators** have access to oversight tools that allow them to review subscription requests, approve or deny access, and generate compliance reports.

7.3.3. Integration with Backend and Dataspace

The frontend communicates with the backend exclusively via secured REST APIs. The plan is for Authentication and session management to be handled through OAuth2/OIDC, integrating Eclipse Dataspace ID when required. Once authenticated, users can perform operations such as posting new services, subscribing to existing ones, or updating access policies. All interactions will be backed by the backend’s coordination with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector and Hyperledger Fabric, ensuring that what the user sees in the interface corresponds to agreements in the dataspace.

7.3.4. Design Principles and Usability

The design of the frontend emphasises clarity and efficiency. Grid layouts and card-based components make navigation straightforward, while consistent typography and spacing provide a coherent aesthetic. Accessibility has been addressed by implementing touch-friendly buttons, responsive breakpoints, and semantic HTML, ensuring usability across a wide range of devices. The user experience follows the principle of progressive disclosure, presenting simple entry points for common tasks while allowing advanced users to configure fine-grained policies and conditions.

7.4. Integration and Testing Strategy in the Alpha Prototype

At this stage, the prototype represents an alpha version of the decentralized framework. The primary goal of this release is not yet full technical maturity, but rather the simulation of complete workflows in order to gather structured feedback from pilot site owners and other stakeholders. By exposing real users to the key interactions such as service publication, subscription requests, contract negotiation, and access enforcement, we ensure that the system evolves in alignment with practical needs and expectations.

7.4.1. Focus on Workflow Simulation

The alpha implementation provides all the core building blocks of the framework: a React frontend, and a Spring Boot backend. What matters most at this stage is that users can walk through the full end to end journey. A pilot site owner, acting as a service consumer, can request access to example services, while being informed of dependencies between services and data requirements abstracting interactions with the EDC. While these workflows are simplified, they are sufficient to illustrate the mechanics of the system and generate meaningful feedback.

7.4.2. Feedback as the Driving Metric

Rather than measuring performance, throughput, or scalability, the alpha focuses on user perception and clarity of interaction. Pilot site owners will be encouraged to evaluate whether the workflows are intuitive, whether the contract terms are presented transparently, and whether policy configurations reflect real governance needs. Feedback will be collected through workshops and questionnaires. This input will determine which features require refinement, which workflows need simplification, and where additional training or documentation may be necessary.

7.4.3. Iterative Improvement through Co-Design

The testing process is deliberately iterative. Each cycle of pilot engagement generates insights that are fed back into the development process. For example, early pilots may highlight the need for more modular service endpoints, clearer subscription approval steps, or improved error handling. By involving site owners and service providers directly in this loop, the framework is co-designed with its end users, ensuring relevance and long-term adoption.

7.4.4. Validation of Audit and Governance Concepts

Even though technical optimization is secondary at this stage, the alpha still validates the governance principles of the framework. The core idea is that the user interface of the framework must explicitly expose the data interexchange in a way that is intuitive for non-technical users.

In conclusion, the integration and testing strategy of the alpha prototype is driven by feedback collection rather than performance metrics. By simulating real workflows for pilot

site owners and documenting their responses, the WILSON framework ensures that the final implementation will be grounded in the actual requirements of those who will operate and benefit from the system.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents a high-level analysis of the blockchain-based decentralized P2P framework requirements and outlines a path forward. It also introduces the alpha version of the implementation, designed primarily as a vehicle for testing user interactions and validating design choices with pilot site owners. At this point, the system does not aim for technical maturity. Instead, its purpose is to simulate the essential workflows, such as service publication, subscription negotiation, and access management, so that feedback can be gathered on usability, clarity, and governance. By deliberately focusing on workflow demonstration rather than full implementation, the alpha ensures that adjustments can be made before significant resources are invested in production-level features.

The project has already encountered the implications of the transition from IDS RAM 4.0 (1) to RAM 5.0 (2). This shift has not only altered the reference model but also changed expectations regarding connector responsibilities, trust anchors, and interoperability layers. WP5 early decision to adopt RAM 5.0 has positioned the framework to remain aligned with the most current version of IDS architecture, which is essential for long-term sustainability. However, this alignment has also introduced complexity, since many original designs were based on RAM 4.0 assumptions. Reconciling these differences has required pragmatic compromises in the alpha and will remain a central theme for the next iterations.

The limitations of the current Eclipse Dataspace Connector also come into focus at this stage. Because access control is enforced only at the granularity of exposed endpoints, providers risk having limited flexibility in defining policies. In practice, this can mean that a single coarse-grained service interface determines all access rights, creating a binary situation rather than supporting nuanced governance. While this limitation cannot be fully solved within the project, it underscores the importance of designing modular endpoints and gathering pilot feedback on where fine-grained control is most critical.

Overall, the alpha prototype confirms the feasibility of combining backend and frontend components to illustrate the intended platform behavior. Its greatest contribution, however, lies in opening up the development process to pilot stakeholders, who can now engage with tangible workflows and provide feedback. The framework is not yet a complete solution but a shared starting point for co-design, iterate, and refinement over the remaining project period.

9. REFERENCES

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10. ANNEX 1. ALPHA VERSION USER MANUAL

This annex provides a walkthrough of the alpha prototype of the decentralized P2P framework. The purpose is to illustrate the user interface and the key workflows that pilot site owners and service providers can simulate in order to provide feedback. The explanations below correspond to the screenshots included in this section.

10.1. Landing page

The landing page is the first point of entry to the platform. It presents the WILSON logo and project colors, ensuring consistency with the brand identity. A clear call-to-action button, "Enter Platform", directs users to the login screen.

Figure 4 Landing Page in decentralized P2P framework

10.2. Login

The login screen enables users to authenticate with the system. In the alpha, this is handled by a basic username and password flow using JWT tokens. Users are asked to enter their credentials and are granted access to the platform according to their role (consumer, provider, administrator). Future iterations will integrate OAuth2/OIDC and/or Eclipse Dataspace ID, but for now the login form ensures that pilot testers can simulate role-based navigation. Feedback is sought on the clarity of the interface, the ease of understanding what credentials are required, and the visibility of error messages when login fails.

Figure 5 Login in decentralized P2P framework

10.3. Register

The registration screen allows new users to create an account. In the alpha, the process requires providing a username, email address, and password, along with selecting whether

the user acts as a service provider or consumer. Organizations can also be specified, enabling multi-tenant scenarios. The form is intentionally minimal, focusing on capturing only the information necessary to simulate workflows. Future releases will include stronger identity checks, Eclipse Dataspace ID integration, and administrative approval.

Figure 6 Register in decentralized P2P framework

10.4. My Subscriptions (internal landing page)

Once authenticated, consumers are directed to the *My Subscriptions* page, which acts as the internal landing screen. This page lists all active subscriptions, along with status indicators (pending, active, cancelled). Each subscription card includes service details, validity dates, and available actions (e.g., cancel or renew). In the alpha, the information shown is partly simulated, but it is sufficient to demonstrate the lifecycle management of services. The aim is to gather feedback on layout, clarity of status indicators, and whether the user can easily understand the state of their subscriptions.

Figure 7 Subscriptions page in decentralized P2P framework

10.5. Manage My Subscription

This screen allows users to manage an active subscription in detail. Besides cancelling a subscription, users can adjust notification preferences (billing alerts, usage warnings, service updates) and download information through the data export options for usage and billing history.

The Danger Zone highlights the cancellation option, making clear that access will end once the current billing period finishes. This page helps users stay informed about their consumption and billing while keeping control over their service relationship

Figure 8 Subscriptions manage in decentralized P2P framework

10.6. Browse Services

The *Browse Services* screen displays the catalog of services available for subscription. Each service is represented as a card showing its name, description, and pricing information. Consumers can search and filter services, and clicking on a service card opens its detailed view. For pilot users, this page illustrates how a marketplace of services could be presented. The goal is to collect feedback on whether the catalog layout feels navigable, whether the amount of information shown is sufficient to decide on a subscription, and what additional metadata (e.g., provider reputation, service categories) might be helpful.

Figure 9 Browse Services in decentralized P2P framework

10.7. Service Details

The *Service Details* page provides more complete information about a selected service. This includes a description, cost, validity period, and associated policies. A *Subscribe* button allows consumers to initiate a subscription request. In the alpha, policies are presented in simplified form, but the intent is to show how conditions of use are made transparent. Pilot site owners should comment on whether this page makes the terms of service clear and whether additional visual cues (e.g., compliance badges, policy highlights) would aid understanding.

React App

No es seguro 192.168.60.2:3000/services/svc-002

Varios Circe formacion tecnica proyectos rack SPARK EU Funding & Tend... EU Funding & Tend... Dynins

← Back to Services Browse More My Subscriptions

Smart Building IoT Platform

TUE Innovation Lab • IoT Platform €299.99/month Setup: €200.00

★★★★☆ 4.6 (89 reviews)

IoT Sensors Automation Platform

About This Service

Transform your building into a smart, connected ecosystem with our comprehensive IoT platform. This service provides seamless integration with hundreds of sensor types, real-time data streaming, and advanced analytics capabilities. Whether you're managing a single building or a portfolio of properties, our platform scales to meet your needs while ensuring data security and compliance.

Key Features

- ✓ Multi-protocol sensor support (LoRaWAN, WiFi, Zigbee)
- ✓ Automated alert and notification system
- ✓ Edge computing capabilities
- ✓ Data visualization and dashboards
- ✓ Real-time data streaming and processing
- ✓ RESTful and GraphQL API access
- ✓ Device management and configuration
- ✓ Third-party system integrations

Technical Specifications

DATA TYPES COMPLIANCE

Figure 10 Service Details in decentralized P2P framework

10.8. Post New Service

For providers, the *Post New Service* form is the main entry point for publishing services. The interface allows providers to define a service name, price, description, and optional image. In the alpha, these entries are stored in the backend database and made visible in the catalog. The workflow demonstrates how providers can onboard services and manage their lifecycle. Pilot feedback is especially sought on whether the form fields are sufficient, whether guidance on pricing or documentation links is needed, and how the overall process could be simplified.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the following details:

- Browser Tab:** React App
- Address Bar:** No es seguro 192.168.60.2:3000/post-service
- Navigation Bar:** Home button
- Form Fields:**
 - Service Name ***: Text input field with placeholder "Enter service name".
 - Description ***: Text area with placeholder "Describe your service...".
 - Category ***: Dropdown menu with "Select category".
 - Pricing Model ***: Dropdown menu with "Free".
 - API Endpoint URL**: Text input field with placeholder "https://api.yourservice.com/v1".
 - Technical Requirements**: Text area with placeholder "Describe any technical requirements, dependencies, or integration details...".
- Buttons:** "Create Service" and "View My Services".

Figure 11 Post New Service in decentralized P2P framework

10.9. Manage Services

Providers can also view and manage services they have already published. This interface shows current pricing, validity dates, and client subscriptions. Providers may update service details or withdraw services from the catalog. The alpha version keeps the functionality basic but illustrates the key management tasks a provider will perform. In later releases, this will connect directly to contract management and policy enforcement via the Eclipse Dataspace Connector. Feedback from providers should focus on whether the information presented is adequate for decision making and what additional actions they would expect to perform on this screen.

Figure 12 Manage Services in decentralized P2P framework

10.10. Manage Service Detail

When selecting *Manage* on a service card, providers access this overview page. It shows the service’s status, current revenue, number of subscribers, and key performance metrics such as uptime and response time. A recent activity feed highlights subscription changes and usage events. From here, providers can also navigate analytics, pricing, compliance, and client management to maintain full control over their published service.

Figure 13 Manage Service Detail in decentralized P2P framework

10.11. Service View Clients

The *View Clients* screen allows providers to monitor and manage subscribers to a specific service. At the top, summary cards display the number of clients, active subscribers, trial users, and current monthly revenue. Below, detailed entries show each client’s subscription status, usage statistics, billing information, and support interactions. Providers can filter by subscription state (active, trial, pending, cancelled) and use quick actions such as *Manage* or *Contact* to handle client relationships directly.

Figure 14 Service: View Clients in decentralized P2P framework

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